

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
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IMPLEMENTATION OF A NURSE-DRIVEN VENTILATOR WEANING
PROTOCOL AT A COMMUNITY HOSPITAL

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By
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ABSTRACT

This paper will review the benefits of a nurse-driven ventilator weaning protocol (NDVWP) in a community hospital that currently utilizes a physician led weaning approach. Physicians have traditionally guided ventilator weaning, however their weaning trials typically occur once a day. Because of this, there are missed opportunities during the day in which patients could be weaned off the ventilator. Nurse-driven ventilator weaning protocols have been developed to assess clinical factors indicating a patient's eligibility to wean off the ventilator. Nurses are readily available to evaluate patients by virtue of their job. As such, a NDVWP can be utilized in the hospital to expediently start ventilator weaning trials for patients and prevent adverse events associated with prolonged mechanical ventilation.

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BACKGROUND

Mechanical Ventilation (MV) has the benefit of assisting patients with a compromised respiratory system. However, patients requiring MV for a prolonged period of time are at risk for complications. Prolonged mechanical ventilation (PMV) in the intensive care unit (ICU) is associated with increased morbidities such as pulmonary infections, lung trauma, and mortality (Kobayashi, Uchino, Takinami, & Uezono, 2017). Additionally, PMV is related to higher hospital costs (Burns, 2012). Ventilator weaning protocols have been developed to reduce the risks associated with prolonged mechanical ventilation (Burns, 2012).

Traditionally, physicians guided ventilator weaning through experience and personal choice rather than through the use of a ventilator weaning protocol (Arici et al., 2016; Mouro, Hall-Jenssens, & Pamukov, 1998). The ventilator weaning process was uncoordinated and contingent on the clinician guiding the weaning. With non-protocol weaning, nurses would evaluate a patient's eligibility to wean off the ventilator, however weaning success depended on the nurse's experience and autonomy (Knebel, 1996). A nurse's approach to ventilator weaning varied widely and assessments would not yield enough comprehensive information (S. M. Burns, Fahey, Barton, & Slack, 1991). As a result, poor coordination with ventilator weaning can lead to prolonged time on mechanical ventilation, consequently placing patients at higher risk for ventilator associated complications. Thus appropriate weaning protocols provide structure and decrease variation. This improves efficiency and consistency with ventilator weaning and reduces the subjective influence of clinician judgment and experience (Blackwood, Burns, Cardwell, & O'Halloran, 2014)

Nurse-driven ventilator weaning protocols (NDVWP) are strategies used to decrease time on MV (Blackwood, Burns, Cardwell, & Halloran, 2014). These guides assess the patient's readiness to come off the ventilator and provide a step by step weaning method. Nurse-driven ventilator weaning protocols have been shown to decrease ICU length of stay (LOS) and time on MV. Furthermore, NDVWP were reported to be comparably safe to physician-driven ventilator weaning strategies (Danckers et al., 2013). NDVWP have therefore been suggested to be a better method for decreasing time on MV, decreasing prolonged MV associated risks, and decreasing hospital expenditures (Kollef et al., 1997).

Nurses are promptly able to evaluate a patient's changing condition by virtue of their frequent presence at the patient bedside. In institutions that do not have a 24-hour intensivist, NDVWP may serve to assist with MV weaning for eligible patients. This ultimately can lead to better patient outcomes.

Problem Statement

At the project hospital, there is no ventilator weaning protocol available that assesses readiness to wean off the ventilator. Weaning trials are initiated when the overseeing pulmonologist deems the patient is eligible for weaning. This typically occurs once per day during the morning hours. When ventilator weaning trials fail on the initial visit from the pulmonologist, MV weaning is delayed until the next day when the pulmonologist visits the ICU again and reevaluates the patient. Pulmonologists as well as attending nurses have identified a need to apply a NDVWP to decrease length of time on MV and therefore prevent adverse events associated with prolonged mechanical ventilation.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project is to develop a guideline that will educate and train nursing staff on a NDVWP for hospital implementation. Nursing staff will be educated and evaluated on their knowledge/understanding of the guideline prior to NDVWP implementation. The ultimate goal of the project is to decrease time on the mechanical ventilator, decrease risks associated with prolonged mechanical ventilation, and to decrease LOS. The protocol will be designed to standardize the process of weaning ICU patients off the ventilator at the project hospital. In collaboration with the ICU medical director and ICU manager, the protocol will be implemented. At present, the project hospital is establishing an ICU manager role to assist with future implementation of the protocol. The protocol will be implemented once the ICU manager role is established. The purpose of the project will be achieved through a collaborative development of the NDVWP with the ICU medical director and ICU manager and by providing nursing staff with NDVWP education and training. Once the protocol is implemented, there are future plans for pre and post NDVWP implementation data collection, analysis/evaluation of data, and presentation of data to ICU medical director for possible policy development of a NDVWP.

Supporting Framework

A supporting framework has multiple elements to guide a practice change. It can involve multiple steps to methodically describe relationships between variables (Polit, 2017). The Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (PARIHS) was first introduced in 1998 to address the multifaceted nature of how new innovation is

implemented in practice (Smith, 2017). It was extensively used to assist in predicting and explaining how a practice change is implemented and if it would be successful (Harvey & Kitson, 2016).

The PARIHS framework focused on three elements: evidence, context, and facilitation. Collectively, these elements worked together to apply research into clinical practice (Kitson, Harvey, & McCormack, 1998). While the PARIHS framework is useful in the implementation of new innovation, it has some limitations. For example, the wider context (policy level, economy, law, etc.) beyond the local context (department, ward, hospital unit, etc.) for which implementation of a change practice can occur is not easily identified (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). Additionally, the relationships among various elements and sub-elements of the framework were not clearly delineated. The PARIHS framework was criticized for its lack of emphasis on the role of facilitators during implementation, thus the PARIHS framework has since been modified to address these factors (Smith, 2017).

The new integrated-PARIHS framework (iPARIHS; Figure 1) includes four elements: innovation, recipients, context, and facilitation. These elements are dynamic and simultaneous, with each element affecting the outcome of the other (Harvey & Kitson, 2016).

In the iPARIHS framework, innovation is the proposed practice change. This innovation is developed from empirical research, as well as from clinical experiences and patient experiences. Innovation involves assessing the compatibility of a new intervention in an organization, its usability, as well as trialability (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). This framework is improved from the original PARIHS because of its emphasis on

implementation success via the metrics in achievement of implementation goals and outcomes derived from facilitation of the new innovation with its recipients (Harvey & Kitson, 2016).

Recipients, in the framework, refer to individuals affected by the innovation, as well as the individuals who help implement the new intervention. Stakeholders who fall under the category of recipients can include patients, managers, and clinical staff due to their influence in facilitating a new intervention. Some characteristics assessed among recipients are values, beliefs, goals, resources, motivation, and presence of boundaries (Harvey & Kitson, 2016).

Context is an element that focuses on where the new practice change is implemented. There are three levels of context involved; local level, organizational level, and external health system level. The local level involves culture of the organization, learning environment, leadership support, and experience of practice changes in the past. The organizational level consists of the organization's priorities, structure and systems, and willingness to accept new implementations. The external health system level deals with policy development, inter-organizational relationships, and regulating bodies (Harvey & Kitson, 2016).

Lastly, facilitation in the iPARIHS framework ties innovation, recipients and facilitation together. Facilitation evaluates all the elements of a new practice change and makes adjustments for them to be adaptable within the targeted setting. This element involves a facilitator who can influence organizational culture and inspire recipients to adopt a new innovation. Facilitation is the most elaborate element in the iPARIHS

framework as it requires facilitators to have the skills and knowledge to adapt and strategize complex practice changes (Harvey & Kitson, 2016).

While the framework has multiple elements, there is no sequential path to assure success of a new practice change. Facilitators need to constantly re-evaluate and assess for weaknesses that may obstruct successful implementation of a practice change. The iPARIHS framework has the essential keys needed to guide this DNP project regarding a practice change using a NDVWP.

The innovation would be to educate and evaluate nurses on a NDVWP for future implementation in the ICU. There is evidence that NDVWPs have led to decreases in intubation times as well as early extubation (Danckers et al., 2013; Marelich et al., 2000; Roh et al., 2012). Prolonged intubation has been associated with complications such as ventilator associated pneumonia as well as increased hospital costs (Marelich et al., 2000). At the project hospital, management and administration have expressed the need to decrease intubation times for the sake and benefit of patient safety. The NDVWP would also have the potential of decreasing the length of stay in less critically ill patients to accommodate other patients who need intensive care. Hospital resources in the ICU could be utilized more efficiently to assist patients who need a mechanical ventilator. Management and administration are in agreement that implementing a NDVWP would help achieve this goal.

Recipients in this framework involve the nurses administering the protocol. Using this framework, nurses' skills and knowledge would be assessed. Nurses would be trained on the NDVWP and evaluated for future implementation of the new protocol. Ultimately,

intubated patients, 18 years of age or older, would receive the NDVWP and data would be collected on length of intubation and success of extubation.

The ICU will be the context in which NDVWP will be utilized. After discussing the innovation with the ICU medical director and medical administration, there is a readiness to adopt the proposed change once a new ICU manager is established. The culture in the ICU is amenable to practice change that would ultimately benefit the patient.

Multiple facilitators would be involved in the implementation of the new practice change. One facilitator would be the ICU medical director who is a pulmonologist. Collaboratively, the ICU medical director and project author will instruct the nursing staff on a NDVWP to implement in the ICU. The ICU manager would also act as a facilitator assisting with educating the nursing staff and ensuring competency with the NDVWP. Lastly the project author would act as a facilitator, coordinating with the nursing staff, ICU medical director, and ICU manager to assess for strengths and weaknesses to the NDVWP implementation. The iPARIHS framework addresses the factors needed for a successful practice change. While using this framework, adjustments will be made to each factor as the DNP project progresses.

Facilitator Focus and Activity

What the Facilitator Looks at

What the Facilitator Does

Source: Harvey G & Kitson A (2015) Implementing Evidence-Based Practice in Healthcare: A facilitation guide. Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge

Figure 1. Integrated Promotion Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (iPARiHS) Framework.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A review of the literature was conducted to identify and retrieve articles regarding the benefits of a NDVWP. Literature supports NDVWP reducing the risks of prolonged mechanical ventilation, decreasing the time on mechanical ventilation, and reducing the LOS in the ICU. The databases utilized to conduct the search included: CINAHL, Cochrane Library, PubMed, EBSCO, and Google Scholar. Search terms included: nurse driven ventilator weaning, ventilator weaning protocol, ventilator protocol, ventilator liberation protocol, and nurse ventilator liberation protocol. The search was limited to peer reviewed articles published in English from 1997 to 2018. The selected timeframe of 21 years provided a high number of articles related to NDVWP.

A second search was also conducted to identify barriers to implementation of a ventilator weaning protocol. While the same databases were utilized, key terms used included: ventilator weaning barrier(s), ventilator protocol barrier(s), ventilator nurse barrier(s), and nurse ventilator attitude(s). The search was limited to peer reviewed articles from 2000 to 2018 and included national and international studies.

The total search yielded 48 articles, 22 of which were relevant to this project. Seven articles were randomized controlled trials, five were qualitative studies, four were review articles, and three were cohort studies. There was one article found for each of the following categories of research types: review of literature, systematic review, and a quasi-experimental study.

Overview of Mechanical Ventilation

Mechanical ventilation has been used to assist and provide the work of breathing for patients who have a compromised respiratory system and are unable to sustain

sufficient alveolar ventilation. These devices are typically used in intensive care units (ICUs) and long term care facilities (Cawley, 2011). Invasive methods of mechanical ventilation utilize devices that are placed in the patient's upper airway (e.g., endotracheal tube [ET], tracheostomy tube, or nasotracheal tube). Once the airway is secure, the patient's work of breathing is assisted by the ventilator (Cawley, 2011). The ventilator provides a patient with oxygenation while decreasing the patient's work of breathing. This allows patients who have a compromised respiratory system time to recover from their underlying illness (Cawley, 2011).

While a mechanical ventilator is a life supporting measure, it is invasive, costly, and carries the potential for risks and complications (Zhu et al., 2015). Patients who are on prolonged mechanical ventilation are at risk for ventilator associated lung injuries. Ventilator associated pneumonia (VAP) is a common risk/complication of invasive mechanical ventilation. It is defined as pneumonia that occurs 48 hours or more after being placed on invasive mechanical ventilation (Erb et al., 2016). Patients who contract VAP are at risk of prolonged time on a mechanical ventilator, as well as increased mortality, and increased hospital costs and LOS (Ego, Preiser, & Vincent, 2015).

Barotrauma is another risk/complication of mechanical ventilation. It is also associated with increased mortality and morbidity (Anzueto et al., 2004). This can occur with over-distension of the lung during ventilation leading to lung injuries such as a pneumothorax, subcutaneous emphysema, and pneumomediastinum (Anzueto et al., 2004). Additionally, biotrauma can result from barotrauma. Biotrauma is the release of intrinsic mediators that can damage the lungs and other organs as a consequence of being on mechanical ventilation (Kneyber, Zhang, & Slutsky, 2014). The risks and

complications identified can lead to greater difficulty of attaining independence from the ventilator. Consequently, strategies have been developed to wean patients off the mechanical ventilator efficiently and safely.

Ventilator Weaning Protocols

Ventilator weaning protocols are structured guides to help reduce and/or discontinue MV support (Blackwood, Burns, Cardwell, & Halloran, 2014). These guides typically contain three components: 1) criteria to assess readiness for ventilator weaning, 2) structured method to reduce ventilator support, and 3) criteria to determine if a patient is eligible to be extubated (Blackwood, Burns, Cardwell, & Halloran, 2014). These guides can help reduce variations in a clinician's decision to wean or extubate. Without using a protocol, a clinician's decision to wean is often influenced by personal experience, subjectivity, and training (Blackwood, Burns, Cardwell, & Halloran, 2014). Ventilator weaning protocols have been associated with decreased LOS in the ICU, improved patient outcomes, and independence from the ventilator (Girard et al., 2017; Zhu et al., 2015).

A recurring strategy found in the literature is the use of spontaneous breathing trials (SBT) for ventilator weaning (Esteban et al., 1995; Robertson et al., 2008; Rose, 2015). These trials assess a patient's aptitude to breathe independently. Patients on a MV are put on continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) or a low level of pressure support for 30-60 minutes at a time. Based on the patient's physiologic status and response to the trials, they are weaned off the mechanical ventilator.

Traditionally, patients were weaned off a MV using reduction of inspiratory pressure in pressure support mode or adjusting the ventilator rate in synchronized

intermittent mandatory ventilation. The traditional method takes more time and increases LOS in the hospital due to the incremental decrease of the ventilator settings (Girard et al., 2017). Whereas SBT provides single opportunities to demonstrate independent breathing while ventilator support is at a minimum. The SBT has become the preferred method to assess a patient's readiness to be weaned from the ventilator due to its ease and quickness of implementation (Esteban et al., 2008; Rose, 2015).

Nurse Driven Ventilator Weaning

Traditionally, physicians made the decision for ventilator weaning without the use of protocols. Recent data suggests that ventilator weaning protocols may effectively wean patients off the ventilator faster than physician lead weaning (Girard et al., 2017). The use of a ventilator weaning protocol helps assess a patient's readiness to wean off the mechanical ventilator and provides steps for weaning. Due to their efficacy, ventilator weaning protocols have been recommended for managing mechanically ventilated patients (Girard et al., 2017).

Nurses play an important role in weaning patients off a mechanical ventilator. Extubation time was statistically significant, at 2 hours and 13 minutes shorter ($p < 0.001$) with a nurse-driven ventilator weaning protocol (NDVWP) compared to physician driven protocols (Danckers et al., 2013). The same study also demonstrated a decrease in LOS with a median duration of 5 days in the ICU with NDVWP versus physician led weaning of 7 days (Danckers et al., 2013).

With the use of ventilator weaning protocols, there is a question of its safety in weaning patients. A study that evaluated the feasibility of a NDVWP, compared to physician led ventilator weaning, showed no differences in mortality between patients in

the NDVWP group and the physician led weaning group. There was a higher rate of successful weaning among patients provided with a NDVWP versus physician led weaning ($p=0.039$). Additionally, there was a reported cost saving of \$42,960 per patient in the NDVWP group versus the physician led weaning group (Kollef et al., 1997).

The benefit of a NDVWP is the nurses' availability to assess patient change in condition. One study demonstrated how a NDVWP was able to reduce time on a mechanical ventilator as well as reduce incidence of ventilator associated pneumonia compared to physician driven weaning. Duration of time on a mechanical ventilator was significantly decreased from 124 hours to 68 hours for patients provided with NDVWPs versus the physician weaning group. Additionally ventilator associated pneumonia was noted to be decreased in the NDVWP group versus the physician led weaning group (Marelich et al., 2000). Evidence continues to validate the benefits of a NDVWP.

Potential Barriers to Ventilator Weaning Protocols

The benefits of ventilator weaning protocols have been documented in multiple studies and demonstrate that these protocols have the potential to reduce risks for patients (Fan et al., 2015; Girard et al., 2017; Gupta, Giehler, Walters, Meyerink, & Modrykamien, 2014; Zhu et al., 2015). However, there are potential barriers that can influence their use. Nurses are best situated to apply ventilator weaning protocols due to their continual presence at the bedside (Eckerblad, Eriksson, Kärner, & Edéll-Gustafsson, 2009). With the expanding role of nurses, there has been discussion of who should initiate the ventilator weaning process; the physician or the nurse (Crocker, 2009). This discussion of responsibility does present challenges based on the nurse's experience, education, and confidence (Eckerblad et al., 2009; Lavelle & Dowling, 2011). These

factors can present as barriers to ventilator weaning protocols depending on the perceptions of nurses (Lavelle & Dowling, 2011).

The nurse's level of familiarity with the patient impacts their decision to start the weaning protocol. Data shows that nurses were less likely to start a weaning protocol if they felt unfamiliar with the patient (Khalafi, Elahi, & Ahmadi, 2016). Nurses are able to create care strategies tailored to each individual patient. When nurses know patients well (understanding facial expressions, body language, physiologic status), they are able to make informed clinical decisions (Eckerblad et al., 2009). Evidence suggests that to improve continuity of care, nurses must spend more time with their patient. A comprehensive understanding of the patient's needs is essential in the nurse's role for ventilator weaning (Khalafi et al., 2016; Lavelle & Dowling, 2011).

A potential barrier to learning the protocol is the culture of the hospital. Manager and peer support have an impact on nurse attitudes towards learning new innovations. Managers serve as role models to nurses and can promote or hinder nurse learning dependent on their attitudes and level of participation. Additionally the presence or absence of peer support can motivate or negatively affect nurse learning (Santos, 2012). Encouraging and optimistic role modeling as well as a mutual vision can promote integration of new evidence based practices (Warren et al., 2016).

Traditionally, physicians decide when and how to wean patients off a MV (Lavelle & Dowling, 2011). However, there is debate regarding NDVWP and its potential effect on physician competency for managing a MV. Protocols can purportedly cause deficiencies in physician's competency to manage mechanical ventilator weaning by decreasing their active role and clinical decision making skills with ventilator

management (Diringer & Yende, 2012; Prasad et al., 2011). Moreover, a NDVWP can allegedly distance physicians from direct patient care due to its initiation by non-physician practitioners (Prasad et al., 2011). These factors can create resistance to the implementation of NDVWPs. While this claim is controversial, recent evidence shows that it has no bearing on physician knowledge of mechanical ventilator management and weaning. A recent retrospective cohort study was conducted to assess physician examinees competency when taking the Critical Care Medicine and American Board of Internal Medicine Certificate. These examinees were exposed to MV weaning protocols (high exposure: 2 or more protocols; low exposure: 0-1 protocol) during their training. Questions pertaining to MV were evaluated. The study showed no difference in competency between the high exposed examinees and low exposed (Diringer & Yende, 2012). Overall, a NDVWP can save time and money, which makes its application beneficial to patient care.

Implementation of the NDVWP is contingent on the collaboration between the ICU manager, ICU medical director, project author, and nurses. Due to administrative changes, there currently is no ICU manager, however the position is in the process of being filled. Initiation of the NDVWP will begin once the position of an ICU manager is established at the project hospital.

Summary

Mechanical ventilation remains a staple in respiratory management for patients with impaired respiratory function (Cawley, 2011). Despite its benefits of assisting patients with breathing, prolonged use does carry increased risk of causing infection as well as lung damage (Zhu et al., 2015). Ventilator weaning protocols have been

developed as strategies to decrease time on mechanical ventilator (Blackwood, Burns, Cardwell, & Halloran, 2014). Literature supports NDVWP reducing the risks of prolonged mechanical ventilation, decreasing the time on mechanical ventilation, and reducing the LOS in the ICU. Nurses play a vital role in implementing ventilator weaning protocols with evidence showing that they can implement protocols safely and with better patient outcomes than physician lead ventilator weaning (Danckers et al., 2013).

Although this strategy is promising, potential barriers such as nurse perceptions and clinical experience can influence a nurse's decision to use ventilator weaning protocols (Lavelle & Dowling, 2011). However, this barrier can be mitigated by increasing continuity of care through better communication as well as time spent at the bedside with the patient. Nurse management and peer support can also assist with implementing new practices (Santos, 2012). This can ultimately help nurses attain a more comprehensive understanding of their patient and help guide their decision to start ventilator weaning (Crocker, 2009; Khalafi et al., 2016). With the current evidence supporting a NDVWP to improve care for patients on a ventilator, this project will focus on developing a NDVWP for intubated patients on a mechanical ventilator in the ICU.

METHODS

This section will describe the design, setting, sample, ethical issues, and development of the project. This quality improvement (QI) project aims to develop a guideline to train nurses regarding a NDVWP that can be implemented in the ICU. The Burns Wean Assessment Program (BWAP; See Appendix A) will be the screening tool utilized by nurses to assess if patients are eligible to be weaned off the ventilator. If patients are deemed eligible for weaning, they will then be weaned off the ventilator utilizing the hospital's established weaning steps (See Appendix B). The goal of utilizing a NDVWP is to reduce the risks associated with prolonged mechanical ventilation. Implementation of the NDVWP is contingent on the role players which are needed to ensure that nurses are utilizing the protocol timely and correctly. These role players include the ICU manager, ICU medical director, and project author. At present, the project hospital is filling the position of the ICU manager. Once the position is filled, NDVWP training will begin.

While the project hospital does not have a NDVWP to evaluate if a patient is eligible for weaning, the project hospital does have a weaning process. The NDVWP will allow nurses to assess a patient's readiness to wean off the ventilator, and if eligible, prompt the nurse to initiate the hospital's established weaning process. The goal of the NDVWP is to decrease the duration a patient is on the ventilator by conducting frequent patient evaluations that would otherwise be done only once per day.

Design

The project will utilize a pre and post evaluation design. A pretest will be used to assess nurse baseline knowledge of ventilator weaning. After weaning education and

training, a posttest will be used to assess nurse comprehension of the new protocol. There is a plan for future implementation of the NDVWP after NDVWP training and once all of the role players are established. At this time no data will be collected for the project. However, once there is successful implementation of the NDVWP, data can be collected. Nurse driven ventilator weaning protocol data will be collected from the hospital's electronic medical records (EMR) and compared to non-NDVWP data of patients who are extubated from a similar time period in which the NDVWP is implemented.

Setting and Sample

This QI project will take place in the ICU at a 350-bed community hospital located in the San Fernando Valley. The NDVWP guideline will be implemented in the hospital's 20-bed ICU where there are 10 nurses, one charge nurse, one respiratory therapist (RT), and one nurse manager available at all times. The ICU will be the context for which the NDVWP guideline will be implemented. The sample will include all day shift nurses who are eligible for caring for patients on mechanical ventilation. Training for the NDVWP will be provided by the ICU medical director, ICU manager, and the project author. The NDVWP training will occur one month prior to implementation of the NDVWP to allow ample time for nurses to attend training sessions. The ICU medical director, ICU manager, and project author will assess nurse competencies when executing the NDVWP prior to implementation.

Ethical Issues

The project proposal has been submitted to the Institutional Review Board (IRB) at California State University, Los Angeles for evaluation and approval. The DNP project did not meet the definition of "Human Subjects Research" as there will be no data

collected or human subjects observed for this project. Currently, the project hospital does not have an IRB. However, permission to implement the NDVWP has been obtained from the ICU medical director. At the time of IRB application submission, the ICU manager role became vacant and has since been in the process of being filled. No patient data will be collected for this project. Instead this project will aim to produce a guideline for implementation of a NDVWP in a hospital.

At the time the NDVWP can be successfully implemented with the appropriate role players in place, data collection can be recorded through the project hospital's EMR. Once the pilot has finished, the data collected from all mechanically ventilated patients will be extracted from the hospital's EMR and de-identified by the hospital's manager of clinical documentation. This information will then be securely delivered to the project author for analysis. The data will be kept in a locked file box in the project author's office.

Implementation Process of NDVWP Guideline

The project author presented a proposal to the ICU medical director for the NDVWP, which included background, plans for development of a NDVWP, and goals for implementation. In collaboration with the ICU medical director and ICU manager, the NDVWP will be tailored to the resources and needs for the project hospital. Presently, the position for an ICU manager role is being filled. This role is critical to ensure nurse compliance with the NDVWP. Once the ICU manager position is filled, the implementation process can begin.

When implemented, the NDVWP will occur on the nurse's day shift hours. The projected time frame will be 7am to 7pm during the routine hours of the nurse's day shift.

This specific timeframe was selected due to the number of staff present on the ICU and accessibility to pulmonologists and respiratory therapists. Recipients of the project will be the nurses receiving NDVWP training as well as the NDVWP instructors (Project author, ICU medical director, and ICU manager). Once the NDVWP is able to be implemented, they will also be the facilitators of the project. Facilitators of the project include nurses and the pulmonologists. Facilitators will also be educated on NDVWP one month prior to implementation of protocol.

NDVWP Training

Classes will be held three times per week to educate all day-shift ICU nurses about the NDVWP. Classes will last 30-45 minutes to discuss the instrument and strategies for NDVWP. These classes will be led by the ICU medical director, ICU manager, or project author. Standardized instructional material will be provided so that there is no variation in the education received by the nurses. Nurses will be trained on the BWAP. Prior to the class, a pretest will be given to the nurses to assess their baseline knowledge of ventilator weaning. After the pretest, nurses will be given educational materials and handouts summarizing the steps for NDVWP. Class instructors will utilize a teach-back method to assess comprehension of the training. The teach-back method has been shown confirm that the individual understands what is being taught and that the individual being taught is able to explain his/her understanding of the teaching (Farris, 2015). A posttest will be given after education and training is provided to evaluate nurse understanding of the protocol.

Instrument

When ready for implementation, the BWAP will be utilized to assess patient's readiness to be weaned off the ventilator. This program consists of a checklist evaluating 26 factors regarding readiness for weaning. It is a scoring instrument that reduces the variability in managing mechanically ventilated patients. This tool has been used since the 1990s with literature supporting its success in identifying a patient's readiness to wean (Jiang et al., 2014; Yazdannik, Salmani, Irajpour, & Abbasi, 2012). The instrument utilizes 26 questions with three item responses: (a) yes, (b) no, (c) not assessed. The number of yes responses is then divided by 26 to obtain the score. A score of greater than 50 indicates that the patient is a good candidate for weaning (Burns et al., 2010). Once the NDVWP is implemented, ventilator weaning trials will start when patients are able to score over 50 on the BWAP.

Data Collection

This DNP project will not collect any data. However it will help provide direction on how to collect data once the protocol is implemented at the project hospital. At present the BWAP questionnaire is not formally integrated into the hospital's EMR. Nurses will document their findings via the BWAP questionnaires provided to them. Data will include: (a) patient's age, (b) gender, (c) BWAP score, (d) diagnosis (e) cause of respiratory failure, (f) time of intubation, (g) adverse events after intubation (g) time of extubation, (h) LOS in ICU, extubation attempts, and (i) incidence of re-intubation after extubation. The sum of data will be collected at the end of each month

Evaluation

A full evaluation regarding efficacy of the NDVWP will occur after its potential implementation. The primary goal of the NDVWP is to reduce the risks associated with prolonged mechanical ventilation and ICU LOS. Pre-protocol data will be collected corresponding to the same time frame the project will be implemented. Pre-NDVWP and post NDVWP data will be collected during the same months to account for seasonal causes of illness. Pre-protocol data will be retrieved from the hospital's EMR and de-identified. During the implementation of the NDVWP, data related to the duration on mechanical ventilation (from time of intubation to extubation), ICU LOS, and rate of ventilator associated complications will be evaluated. Additionally, data on successful ventilator weaning from nurses will be obtained. A biostatistician will be implemented to analyze the data and provide a comparison report between pre-protocol and post-protocol ventilator weaning. The results will be presented to the ICU medical director and ICU manager. Depending on the results, the NDVWP (with the possibility of modifications) will be proposed to the hospital administration as a new ventilator weaning policy.

ANTICIPATED RESULTS

The NDVWP is expected to decrease time on mechanical ventilation through early assessments of a patient's readiness to wean off the ventilator. Once patients are extubated from the ventilator, their likelihood of transitioning out of the ICU will be better. This can ultimately decrease the use of hospital resources leading to decreased costs. Additionally, patients requiring mechanical ventilation can have easier access to a ventilator as a result of more readily available hospital resources.

Workflow for nurses overseeing mechanically ventilated patients is also anticipated to be improved through utilization of a NDVWP. Nurses can promptly assess clinical factors related to ventilator weaning through use of the BWAP and initiate the ventilator weaning process if patients are deemed eligible for weaning. Through NDVWP training, nurses will gain a better understanding of ventilator weaning which they can apply to prospectively attain better patient outcomes.

Based on the anticipated results of the NDVWP, both nurses and clinicians can provide input to modify and improve the NDVWP that best serves the needs of the patients. While the NDVWP is meant to assist nurses and clinicians with ventilator weaning, ongoing evaluation of the NDVWP will be conducted to ensure better patient outcomes.

DISCUSSION

An implemented NDVWP can provide structure and mitigate inconsistency with ventilator weaning without a protocol. The NDVWP also has the potential to decrease adverse events (e.g., pulmonary infections, lung trauma, mortality) associated with prolonged mechanical ventilation through initiating ventilator weaning earlier.

Implementation and success of the NDVWP is contingent on the facilitators (ICU medical director, ICU manager, project author) who are there to enforce the protocol. The NDVWP was brought to hospital administration and approved for implementation, however during the implementation process, the facilitator role of ICU manager became absent. Without all facilitators present, it would be difficult to ensure that nurses were consistently utilizing the protocol. In a collaborative effort to resume implementing a NDVWP in the future, a guideline for future implementation of NDVWP was proposed. Once the ICU manager role is filled, the NDVWP will be implemented in the hospital's ICU.

With evidence showing that a NDVWP is comparatively safe, if not better, than physician-driven ventilator weaning and can decrease time on MV through early ventilator weaning, it is suggested that a NDVWP be implemented at institutions where there are currently no ventilator weaning protocols. Ongoing evaluation regarding NDVWP efficacy will be conducted once the NDVWP is implemented. Future research regarding NDVWPs is recommended to assess how these protocols can impact costs at community hospitals. The manuscript will be submitted for publication (See Appendix C)

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APPENDIX A

BURNS WEAN ASSESSMENT PROGRAM

Burns Wean Assessment Program checklist			
Patient _____			
Yes	No	Not assessed	General assessment
___	___	___	1. Hemodynamic status stable (pulse rate, cardiac output)?
___	___	___	2. Free from factors that increase or decrease metabolic rate (seizures, temperature, sepsis, bacteremia, hypothyroidism/hyperthyroidism)?
___	___	___	3. Hematocrit >25% (or baseline)?
___	___	___	4. Systemically hydrated (weight at or near baseline, balanced intake and output)?
___	___	___	5. Nourished (serum albumin >2.5 mg/dL, parenteral/enteral feedings maximized)? (If albumin is low and anasarca or third spacing is present, score for hydration should be no)
___	___	___	6. Electrolytes within normal limits? (including calcium, magnesium, phosphorus) Correct calcium for albumin level
___	___	___	7. Pain controlled? (subjective determination)
___	___	___	8. Adequate sleep/rest? (subjective determination)
___	___	___	9. Appropriate level of anxiety and nervousness? (subjective determination)
___	___	___	10. Absence of bowel problems (diarrhea, constipation, ileus)?
___	___	___	11. Improved general body strength/endurance (eg, out of bed in chair, progressive activity program)?
___	___	___	12. Findings on chest x-radiograph improving?
Yes	No	Not assessed	Respiratory assessment
<i>Gas flow and work of breathing</i>			
___	___	___	13. Eupneic respiratory rate and pattern (spontaneous respirations <25/min, without dyspnea, no use of accessory muscles) This item is assessed with the patient off ventilator support while parameters in items 20-23 are measured.
___	___	___	14. Absence of adventitious breath sounds (rhonchi, rales, wheezing)?
___	___	___	15. Secretions thin and minimal?
___	___	___	16. Absence of neuromuscular disease/deformity?
___	___	___	17. Absence of abdominal distention/obesity/ascites?
___	___	___	18. Oral endotracheal tube ≥ 7.5 or trach ≥ 6.5
<i>Airway clearance</i>			
___	___	___	19. Cough and swallow reflexes adequate?
<i>Strength</i>			
___	___	___	20. Negative inspiratory pressure ≤ 20 cm H ₂ O
___	___	___	21. Positive expiratory pressure ≥ 30 cm H ₂ O
<i>Endurance</i>			
___	___	___	22. Spontaneous tidal volume >5 mL/kg?
___	___	___	23. Vital capacity >10 to 15 mL/kg?
<i>Arterial blood gases</i>			
___	___	___	24. pH 7.30-7.45
___	___	___	25. P _a CO ₂ approximately 40 mm Hg (or baseline) with minute ventilation <10 L/min (evaluated while patient is on ventilatory support)
___	___	___	26. P _a O ₂ >60 mm Hg with fraction of inspired oxygen <40%

To score the assessment, divide the number of yes responses by 26.

Descriptions and definitions of factors in the Burns Wean Assessment Program (BWAP)^a

General factors

1. Hemodynamic stability: Stable heart rate and rhythm and blood pressure without the use of vasoactive agents (eg, as needed anti-hypertensive medications, infusions of vasopressors with the exception of low-dose dopamine or dobutamine) or any oral agents administered on an as-needed or stat basis to control heart rate or blood pressure.
2. Metabolic stability: Sepsis, active infection, thyroid disarray. The white blood cell count and differential and other indices of infection or active metabolic processes are used for the interpretation.
3. Hematocrit: $\geq 25\%$. Hematocrit is evaluated in conjunction with evidence of bleeding, use of blood products, and so on.
4. Electrolytes: Stable only if repletion of electrolytes and/or treatment of same has not occurred.
5. Nutrition: Evaluated with a number of indices and clinical assessments as available. In patients in stable condition, serum levels of albumin/prealbumin may be used in conjunction with provision of feeding. In patients without available nutrition markers, an assessment of whether the patient is receiving what has been ordered is used in conjunction with absorption.
6. Hydration: Evaluation of intake, output, and weight. This item is viewed as a cumulative and 24-hour evaluation. For example, if a patient's weight is more than 3 kg heavier than the weight at the time of admission (or dry weight), the score is negative. For patients with low albumin stores and third spacing (anasarca, etc), scores are negative.
7. Anxiety (subjective factor): Scoring anxiety requires a response from the patient. If a patient cannot respond to questions about anxiety, the factor is scored as not assessed. A no response is recorded when the anxiety is not controlled. Bedside clinicians can assess anxiety by using a scale (1=least, 10=most). For patients who say they are anxious, the clinician may ask if they feel they need something to reduce their nervousness. When patients have a high score or request anxiety relief, this item is scored negatively.
8. Sleep/rest (subjective factor): As for item 7 but with questions about sleep and/or rest.
9. Comfort (subjective factor): As for item 7 but with questions related to comfort (or pain, if present)
10. Bowels: An evaluation of ileus or abnormal bowel function (no bowel movement in 3 days, diarrhea, etc)
11. General body strength and endurance conditioning: This factor is evaluated relative to previous functional activity and state. The score is negative if progressive activity is not occurring (movement from supine in bed to dangling, holding self upright at side of bed, standing with help, marching in place at bedside, etc). If a patient is able to sit in a chair at bedside, progressive increase in time in the chair is desirable. An activity regimen that is progressing with the help of a physical therapist is also a positive finding.
12. Chest radiograph: A return to baseline findings or improvement in findings compared with the previous radiograph. New abnormal findings result in a no score.

Respiratory factors

Factors that affect gas flow and work of breathing

13. Eupneic respiratory rate and pattern: Both must be present for a positive score. Respirations $>25/\text{min}$ (sustained) is scored negatively, as is any pattern of breathing that is abnormal (eg, chest abdominal asynchrony).
14. Breath sounds: Any adventitious sounds result in a score of no.
15. Abdominal distension: Obesity, ascites, or distention from ileus result in a negative score.
16. Neuromuscular disease or deformities: Any condition that affects respiratory function, such as neuromyopathies, severe scoliosis, stroke with defects.
17. Secretions: Both the amount and consistency of the secretions are noted. For a positive score, secretions should be thin and scant (clinicians look at suctioning frequency in addition to the type of secretion quality and quantity).
18. Endotracheal or tracheostomy tube size: threshold is ≥ 7.5 mm (endotracheal tube) or ≥ 6.0 (tracheostomy).

Ability to maintain a patent airway

19. Airway clearance: Ability to cough and swallow.

Respiratory muscle strength and endurance^b

20. Negative inspiratory pressure: The threshold is ≤ 20 cm H₂O.
21. Positive expiratory pressure: The threshold is ≥ 30 cm H₂O.
22. Spontaneous tidal volume: ≥ 5 mL/kg
23. Vital capacity: \geq Triple tidal volume. Measuring vital capacity is difficult in patients who are intubated but is attempted if a patient can follow directions.

Arterial blood gases

24. pH: 7.30-7.45
25. PaCO₂ and minute ventilation: PaCO₂ 40 mm Hg or baseline value and minute ventilation ≤ 10 L/min. These 2 parameters are viewed together. A patient's baseline PaCO₂ (may be substituted for the threshold value). The thresholds for both PaCO₂ and minute ventilation must be met to be scored positively. For example, a PaCO₂ of 40 mm Hg with a minute ventilation of 20 L/min is scored as no.
26. PaO₂: The threshold is 60 mm Hg with low-level positive end-expiratory pressure (eg, 5 cm H₂O) and fraction of inspired oxygen $\leq 40\%$.

APPENDIX B**PROJECT HOSPITAL'S ESTABLISHED WEANING METHOD****Weaning Steps:**

Weaning Steps

1. Continuous Positive Airway Pressure Weaning Protocol With Pressure Support Ventilation (CPAP/PSV)
 1. If SAT, DE and DWP criteria are met, change ventilator mode from current A/C mode to CPAP, PEEP 5 CmH₂O and Pressure Support Ventilation Mode of 10.
2. Start Weaning process for 2 hours.
3. If tolerated, obtain ABG after 2-hour period
4. Call ordering physician with ABG results.
5. If the ordering physician is satisfied with the ABG results, obtain extubation orders and Supplemental Oxygen orders.
6. Obtain Medication orders if applicable.

Oxygen Titration

1. Maintain SaO₂ greater than 92%

Note: SAT: Spontaneous Awakening Trial; ABG: Arterial Blood Gas; A/C: assist control; CPAP: continuous positive airway pressure; DE: Daily Evaluation; DWP: Daily Weaning Parameters; PEEP: Positive end-expiratory pressure

(VPH, 2017)

APPENDIX C

**GUIDE TO IMPLEMENTATION OF A NURSE DRIVEN VENTILATOR
WEANING PROTOCOL AT A COMMUNITY HOSPITAL**

Guide to Implementation of a Nurse-Driven Ventilator Weaning Protocol

At a Community Hospital

By

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Introduction

Mechanical ventilation (MV) is utilized to provide breathing support for patients with compromised respiratory systems (Cawley, 2010). While MV is helpful in respiratory support, prolonged MV is associated with increased injuries including pulmonary trauma, lung infections, and mortality (Kobayashi, Uchino, Takinami, & Uezono, 2017). Consequently, ventilator weaning protocols were developed to reduce the risks associated with prolonged MV.

There is evidence showing that a Nurse Driven Ventilator Weaning Protocol (NDVWP) can reduce morbidities associated with mechanical ventilation. As such, these protocols have been implemented to decrease ventilator associated injuries.

Nurse-driven ventilator weaning protocols are guides to evaluate a patient's readiness to liberate from the ventilator and provide a step by step weaning strategy. Evidence shows that these protocols can decrease time on MV, decrease intensive care unit (ICU) length of stay, and are comparatively safe as physician-driven ventilator weaning methods. The Burn's Wean Assessment Program (BWAP; See Appendix A) has been a time tested instrument that is effective in weaning patients from the ventilator (Burns et al., 2010). The present guideline will utilize this tool to assess readiness for ventilator weaning.

The following guideline will provide instructions on how to implement a NDVWP in the ICU. The aim of the guideline is to 1) educate and evaluate nurse staff comprehension of NDVWP 2) implement BWAP 3) Evaluate effectiveness of BWAP on mechanically ventilated patients 4) analyze data for potential policy development at the project hospital.

Implementation Plan

Outlined in this section are components necessary for NDVWP implementation:

- A. Practice environment.
- B. Training and Competency
 - a. Pretest
 - b. Burns Wean Assessment Program Training
 - c. Posttest
- C. Data Collection
- D. Data Analysis
- E. Evaluation

Practice Environment

NDVWP training location

A quiet room that can accommodate nursing staff for training session will be required. Pretests and Posttests will be provided during training. Burn's Wean Assessment program handouts (See Appendix B) will be provided outlining use of the tool. Standardized instructions will be utilized in training so that there will be no variation in education given to nurses.

The ICU will be the practice setting for the NDVWP. The protocol will be directed towards intubated patients. Each nurse must receive NDVWP training prior to utilizing the protocol. Questionnaires for the BWAP will be provided to nurses caring for intubated patients. These questionnaires will help evaluate patient eligibility for weaning. No identifying information will be recorded to preserve patient privacy. Nurses are encouraged to talk to NDVWP instructors for any enquiries concerning NDVWP

application. Double checks will be conducted to evaluate BWAP questionnaire to assure patient eligibility for ventilator weaning. Ventilator weaning will start based on questionnaire results. A patient deemed eligible for weaning will be started on weaning trials.

Training and Competency

Curriculum has been developed utilizing active learning/teaching strategies (Bradshaw & Hultquist, 2017). Before BWAP training begins, each nurse will be provided a pretest to assess baseline knowledge of ventilator weaning. This test will cover some of the criteria needed for ventilator weaning. After quizzing, test answers will be discussed with the nurses. The aim of the test is to identify some of the knowledge deficits nurses may have with ventilator weaning. After testing and discussion, instructors will educate nurses regarding the BWAP.

Burns Wean Assessment Program

Instructors will educate nurses about the BWAP which will be the primary instrument to evaluate a patient's readiness to wean off the ventilator. This training will include the instrument (Burns Wean Assessment Program), clinical factors related to ventilator weaning, when to initiate the protocol, and what to document. Training sessions will range from 30-45 minutes to allow for any inquiries regarding the protocol.

The BWAP is a 26 part questionnaire that helps reduce practice variability with ventilator weaning. These 26 parts are elements of care that can influence/impede ventilator weaning and are used to help track patient's clinical progress to signal if a patient is ready for weaning. There are three item responses to the questions: (a) yes, (b) no, (c) not assessed. The number of yes responses is divided by 26 to obtain the score. A

score greater than 50 signifies that the patient has a high potential for successful ventilator weaning. A second nurse with NDVWP training will help validate answers on the BWAP prior to initiating ventilator weaning.

The BWAP addresses clinical factors related to ventilator weaning. These include pulmonary and non-pulmonary factors that can indirectly influence the patient's ability to wean off the ventilator. Nurses will be educated on factors such as hemodynamics, nutrition, work of breathing, strength of breathing, and arterial blood gas conditions that are evaluated for patients who may be considered ready for weaning.

The NDVWP will be initiated after 3 consecutive days of mechanical ventilation as there is evidence suggesting adverse (e.g., increased length of stay, death, etc.) outcomes after 72 hours of mechanical ventilation (Burns et al., 2010). After discussion with the project hospital's ICU director, the NDVWP will be piloted during the day shift (7am-7pm). Nurses will be instructed to utilize the BWAP starting at 7am and at least every 4 hours thereafter (e.g., 7am, 12pm, and 7pm). This time frame for application of the BWAP was chosen by the ICU because of its convenience for nurses and availability of resources (e.g., accessibility of respiratory therapist, intensivist, case managers, etc.). Per nursing judgment, nurses are encouraged to use the BWAP beyond the requested time intervals, if they feel the patient may be eligible for weaning. The NDVWP will be evaluated after 3 months of implementation, and based on its results, the decision to implement the protocol 24 hours a day will be made.

A posttest after training will be conducted to assess nurse comprehension of training. Instructors will be available to answer any questions during training session. A teach back method will be conducted to assess nurses comprehension of the learned

material. Nurses will sign off competency sheets regarding NDVWP which will be placed in their employment files after training is completed.

Documentation

Nurses will be able to answer the BWAP with the paper questionnaire provided to them. Each nurse will paper chart to record data regarding the NDVWP. Once the hospital's electronic medical records (EMR) is able to accommodate data recording specific to NDVWP, nurses can then record data through the hospital's EMR. Data recorded will include:

- Patient's age
- Gender
- BWAP Score
- Diagnosis
- Cause of respiratory failure
- Time of intubation
- Adverse events after intubation
- Time of extubation
- Length of stay in the ICU
- Extubation attempts
- Incidence of re-intubation after extubation.

All information will be de-identified upon collection. The sum of data will be collected at the end of each month. Efficacy of NDVWP can be evaluated through comparison of pre protocol data and post protocol data. Pre protocol data will be evaluated corresponding to the same time frame the NDVWP will be implemented.

Evaluation

The NDVWP is intended to be piloted for 3 months. Data collected will be compared to pre-protocol data to assess for efficacy. A statistician will analyze and compose the data for review. Data analysis will be presented to hospital administration for evaluation, modification, and potential policy development. The goal is to have the NDVWP extended from the day shift to 24 hours per day.

Conclusion

Early assessment of mechanically ventilated patients can help decrease prolonged mechanical ventilation and the morbidities associated with it. Nurses are aptly positioned to assess patients promptly by virtue of their position. Because of this, NDVWPs have been developed to examine a patient's readiness to be weaned off the ventilator. Evidence has shown that a NDVWP is comparatively safe as physician-driven ventilator weaning. Initiating a NDVWP can potentially decrease adverse events associated with prolonged mechanical ventilation, decrease hospitalization time, and decrease hospital costs. With existing evidence supporting a NDVWP to improve care for mechanically ventilated patients, the NDVWP is recommended to be implemented at a community hospital that currently has no ventilator weaning protocol.

Appendix C1

Burns Wean Assessment Program				
	Yes	No	Not Assessed	<u>General Assessment</u>
1.	___	___	___	Hemodynamically stable (pulse, rate, cardiac output)?
2.	___	___	___	Free from factors that increase or decrease metabolic rate (seizures, temperature, sepsis, bacteremia, hypo/hyperthyroid)?
3.	___	___	___	Hematocrit >25% (or baseline)
4.	___	___	___	Systemically hydrated (weight at or near baseline, balanced intake and output)
5.	___	___	___	Nourished (albumin >2.5, parenteral/enteral feedings maximized)? (If albumin is low and anasarca or third spacing is present, score for hydration should be "No".
6.	___	___	___	Electrolyte levels within normal limits (including Ca ⁺⁺ Mg ⁺ , PO ₄ ; correct Ca ⁺⁺ for albumin level)
7.	___	___	___	Pain controlled? (subjective determination)
8.	___	___	___	Adequate sleep/rest (subjective determination)
9.	___	___	___	Appropriate level of anxiety and nervousness? (subjective determination)
10.	___	___	___	Absence of bowel problems (diarrhea, constipation, ileus)?
11.	___	___	___	Improved general body strength/endurance (i.e., out of bed in chair, progressive activity program)?
12.	___	___	___	Chest X-ray improving?
13.	___	___	___	<u>Respiratory Assessment</u> Eupneic respiratory rate and pattern (spontaneous respiratory rate <25/min, without dyspnea, absence of accessory muscle use). *This is assessed off mechanical ventilation while measuring Nos. 20-23.

14. ___ ___ ___ Absence of adventitious breath sounds (rhonchi, rales, wheezing)?
15. ___ ___ ___ Secretions thin and minimal?
16. ___ ___ ___ Absence of neuromuscular disease/deformity?
17. ___ ___ ___ Absence of abdominal distention/obesity/ascites
18. ___ ___ ___ Oral endotracheal tube ≥ 7.5 or tracheostomy tube ≥ 6.5 internal diameter
- Airway Clearance**
19. ___ ___ ___ Cough and swallow reflex adequate
- Strength**
20. ___ ___ ___ Negative inspiratory pressure < -20 cm H₂O
21. ___ ___ ___ Vital Capacity > 10 to 15 mL/kg
- Arterial Blood Gas**
22. ___ ___ ___ pH between 7.30 and 7.45
23. ___ ___ ___ PaCO₂ approximately 40mm Hg (or baseline) with minute ventilation < 10 L/min (evaluated while on ventilator)
24. ___ ___ ___ PaO₂ > 60 on FiO₂ $< 40\%$

Please collect the following data:

1. Patient Age:
2. Gender:
3. BWAP score
4. Diagnosis
5. Cause of respiratory failure
6. Time of intubation
7. Adverse events after intubation

8. Time of extubation
9. LOS in ICU
10. Extubation attempts
11. Incidence of re-intubation after extubation

Appendix C2

Nurse-Driven Ventilator Weaning Education

1. **Hemodynamic Stability**: The primary assessment is perfusion. Absence of clinically significant hypotension (e.g., patient does not require vasopressors)
 - a. Cardiac output: target arterial pressure: 60-65mmHg
 - b. Adequate oxygenation: $PO_2 \geq 60$ Hg on $FIO_2 \leq 40\%$; PEEP $\leq 5-10$ cm H₂O; $PO_2/FIO_2 \geq 150-300$ (Macintyre, 2001).
2. **Metabolic Stability**. Asses for septic state and/or active infection
3. **Hematocrit**: Volume of blood consisting of intact RBCs conveyed as a percentage. Preferred value is $>25\%$ or at patient's baseline. (Burns, Fahey, Barton, & Slack, 1991)
4. **Hydration**: Measurement of intake, output, and weight in a 24 hour evaluation. Assess for weight gain from baseline
5. **Nutrition**: (Serum albumin >2.5 with feeding)
6. **Electrolyte Status**: magnesium, calcium (corrected for albumin), phosphorus. Assess need for electrolyte repletion
7. **Anxiety**: if patient is unable to answer, check "not assessed". If patient reports anxiety is not controlled, consider requesting asking the consulting clinician for anxiolytic.
8. **Assess Bowel Function**: bowel sounds, bowel patterns (diarrhea, constipation, etc.)
9. **General Body Strength**: evaluated relative to patient's previous functional activity. Score is negative if the patient has not had any occurring activity. Positive scores on examination occur if the patient is able to sit at the bedside or chair, or progressing with the assistance of a physical therapist.
10. **Imaging**: if the patient's chest radiograph conveys improvement compared to previous imaging, the score is positive. Any regression or new abnormal findings will yield a negative score.
11. **Respiratory Rate/Pattern**: a eupneic respiratory rate/pattern is required to receive a positive score. Abnormal breathing patterns and/or respirations $>25/\text{min}$ will yield a negative score.
12. **Adventitious Breath Sounds**: assess for abnormal lung sounds such as wheezing/rhonchi

13. **Abdominal Distention**: consider possible ileus or ascites. These findings will yield a negative score.
14. **Neuromuscular Disease/Deformities**: Assess for physical limitations that affect respiratory function (e.g., severe scoliosis, stroke, neuromyopathy)
15. **Secretions**: Patient will receive a positive score for thin and scant secretions
16. **Airway Clearance**: Patient must be able to cough and swallow
17. **Negative Inspiratory Pressure**: helps to measure the patient's inspiratory strength. A patient will receive a positive score for a pressure ≤ 20 cm H₂O
18. **Positive Expiratory Pressure**: breathing against resistance for the purpose of increasing lung volume/tidal volume to improve airway clearance and reduce hyperinflation (Fagevik Olsén, Lannefors, & Westerdahl, 2015). Patient's will test positively with a positive expiratory pressure ≥ 30 cm H₂O.
19. **Spontaneous Tidal Volume**: Tidal volume is the amount of air received with each breath. Patient's will receive a positive score with a tidal volume ≥ 5 mL/kg
20. **Vital Capacity**: is the total volume of air that can be exhaled after inspiring the maximum amount of air possible. Ideally want it 2-3 times more than the tidal volume (e.g., vital capacity > 10 to 15 mL/kg).
21. **Arterial Blood Gas**: measures the oxygen and carbon dioxide tension in blood. Oxygen saturation and bicarbonate concentration are measured in an arterial blood gas as well. These values help identify any acid-base abnormalities.

Appendix C3

Pretest/Posttest

1. Based on your current understanding of mechanical ventilation, what would be some components of patient status you would assess prior to considering ventilator weaning (name at least 4)?

Answer: Hemodynamics, CBC, Pain control, chest imaging, electrolyte status, bowel issues, underlying illness

2. When considering weaning your patient from the ventilator, what is the ideal pH range you would want to see on the arterial blood gas (ABG)?

Answer: pH of 7.30 – 7.45

3. What hematocrit would you want your patient to have prior to extubation?

Answer: Hematocrit: $\geq 35\%$

4. What components of hemodynamics would you assess prior to considering extubation?

Answer: Pulse rate, cardiac output

5. What is the upper limit of respirations/minute you would want your patient to have prior to extubation?

Answer: 24

6. What three electrolytes would you assess/correct pertaining to ventilator weaning?

Answer: Magnesium relaxes smooth muscle in airway. Calcium assists with diaphragmatic muscle contraction. Low phosphorus impairs diaphragmatic contractility.

7. What radiographic test would you request prior to ventilator weaning?

Answer: CXR

8. What are some gastrointestinal complications you might expect with mechanically ventilated patients?

Answer: ileus, constipation, diarrhea

9. You are considering ventilator weaning for your patient. What is the lower limit PaO₂ you would need your patient to have while on the ventilator (given they have an FiO₂ support of $\leq 40\%$)?

Answer: PaO₂: 60

10. You are assessing respiratory muscle strength and endurance in your patient prior to ventilator weaning. What positive expiratory pressure (PEP) would you want to see prior to a ventilator weaning trial?

Answer: PEP ≥ 30 cm H₂O

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